

IMAGE DESCRIPTION GENERATOR USING CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK

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Abstract— The use of image recognition technology has become increasingly popular in recent years, with applications ranging from social media platforms to e-commerce websites. In this project, we use a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) algorithm for image recognition. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are a type of deep neural network that have revolutionized the field of computer vision and image recognition. With their ability to learn complex patterns and features from images, CNNs have become the backbone of many modern computer vision applications.

Keywords- Object recognition, CNN, MobileNetV2, TensorFlow, image processing, deep learning, computer vision, Keras, OpenCV.

I. INTRODUCTION

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are a type of deep neural network that have revolutionized the field of computer vision and image recognition. With the ability to learn complex patterns and features from images, CNNs have become the backbone of many modern computer vision applications. From self-driving cars to facial recognition, CNNs are powering some of the most advanced technologies of our time. In this seminar paper, we will explore the fundamentals of CNNs, including their architecture, and process. Overall, this seminar paper will provide a comprehensive overview of CNNs, their architecture, and training process. It will serve as a valuable resource for anyone interested in computer vision and deep learning, as well as those looking to apply CNNs to real-world problems.

II. CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK

The most popular kind of neural network used to solve image processing issues is the convolutional neural network. Convolutional neural networks can be used in projects involving natural language processing as well, and you've definitely seen them in action anywhere a computer is detecting things in an image. One of the key reasons they are so crucial to deep learning and artificial intelligence today is the fact that they are useful for these quickly expanding fields.

It becomes clear why convolutional neural networks are so successful at processing and classifying pictures once you get how they operate and what distinguishes them from other

neural networks. But first, let's consider a standard neural network. An input layer, hidden layers, and an output layer are all present in a standard neural network (Fig. 1). While the hidden layers process these inputs, the input layer accepts inputs in a variety of formats. The results of the calculations and extractions are subsequently delivered by the output layer. Each of these layers has neurons that are linked to neurons in the layer below, and every neuron in each layer is weighted differently. This indicates that you are not assuming anything regarding the data being fed into the network. Excellent in most cases, but not when working with photos or a language.

Fig 1

Since convolutional neural networks (Fig. 2) treat data as spatial, they operate differently. Neurons aren't coupled to every neuron in the preceding layer; rather, they are only connected to those that are nearby and are all the same weight. The network maintains the spatial component of the data set due to the links' simplicity. It indicates that your network doesn't believe an eye is on the entire picture. The filtering method used in this kind of network is referred to as convolutional. Consider how intricate an image is. It is made simpler by a convolutional neural network so that it may be processed and understood more easily. Convolutional neural networks have numerous layers, just like regular neural networks. The convolutional layer and the pooling layer are two of the layers that set it apart. But it will also have a ReLU or rectified linear unit layer and a fully connected layer, just

like other neural networks. In order to ensure non-linearity as the data passes through each layer of the network, the ReLU layer serves as an activation function. Without it, the dimensionality that we wish to keep in the data being fed into each layer would be lost. In the meantime, you can classify your data set using the fully linked layer.

Fig 2

Let's start with the convolutional layer since it is the most crucial. A filter is applied to an array of picture pixels to make it work. A so-called convolved feature map is the result. Comparable to viewing an image through a window, it lets you see details that you might not otherwise be able to see. The pooling layer follows. This shrinks the sample size for a specific feature map, or down samples it. Additionally, by lowering the quantity of parameters the network must process, processing becomes much faster. This produces a pooled feature map as the result. There are two methods for doing this: maximum pooling, which simply takes the average of all inputs from a certain convolved feature, and average pooling, which simply takes the maximum input. Through these actions, which amount to feature extraction, the network creates a picture of the image data in accordance with its own mathematical rules. You must enter the completely linked layer if you wish to perform classification. You'll need to flatten everything out to accomplish this. Just keep in mind that a neural network with more complicated connections can only handle linear data. Convolutional neural networks can be trained in several ways. Unsupervised learning techniques can be used when working with unlabeled data. Using autoencoders is one of the most well-liked methods for accomplishing this. As a result, you can conduct calculations in the first section of the convolutional neural network while fitting data into a space with few dimensions. After doing this, you must reconstruct using additional layers that up-sample the data you already have. Utilizing generative adversarial networks, or GANS, is an additional choice. You train two networks using a GAN. The second is a discriminative network, whereas the first provides you with synthetic data samples that should mimic data from the training set. It ought to be able to tell the real model apart from the artificial one.

It's actually fairly easy to understand how convolutional and recurrent neural networks vary from one another. A recurrent neural network, as the name suggests, feeds input back into

itself, in contrast to a convolutional neural network, which is a feedforward network that filters spatial data. Recurrent neural networks are therefore more suited to sequential data.

MobileNetV2 is a computationally efficient convolutional neural network (CNN) that is ideal for usage on mobile and embedded devices. It is made up of depth wise separable convolutions, which divide the standard convolution operation into two layers: a depthwise convolution, which applies a single filter to each input channel, and a pointwise convolution, which applies a 1x1 filter to combine the depthwise convolution's outputs.

MobileNetV2 is included in the TensorFlow framework, and the pre-trained weights may be downloaded via the TensorFlow Hub. MobileNetV2 open-source implementations are also available in other deep learning frameworks like as PyTorch and Keras.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Mingxing Tan and Quoc V. Le [1] propose a set of new scaling methods to design smaller and faster EfficientNet models. These methods include a new compound scaling method that jointly scales up the depth, width, and resolution of the network, and a new training scheme that involves progressively increasing the image resolution during training. The authors evaluate the new EfficientNetV2 models on several benchmark datasets and show that they outperform previous state-of-the-art methods while requiring fewer parameters and less computational resources.

Alexey Dosovitskiy, et al. [2] propose a vision transformer (ViT) that divides an image into fixed-size patches and treats each patch as a sequence of flattened vectors. The patches are then fed into a transformer encoder that learns to attend to relevant patches and aggregate their information to classify the image. The authors evaluate the ViT on several benchmark datasets and show that it achieves state-of-the-art performance on image classification tasks while requiring fewer parameters than existing convolutional neural network architectures. The paper also provides insights into the role of attention mechanisms in visual recognition and the importance of pre-training for improving performance on downstream tasks.

Yifan Chen, et al. [3] In this paper, the authors propose Trans2Seg, a model that takes an image as input, encodes it using a transformer-based encoder, and then decodes the encoded information to produce instance segmentation masks. Unlike previous instance segmentation methods that use convolutional neural networks, the Trans2Seg model is fully based on transformers, which allows it to capture long-range dependencies and global context more effectively. The authors evaluate the Trans2Seg model on several benchmark datasets and show that it achieves state-of-the-art performance on instance segmentation tasks while requiring fewer parameters than existing methods. The paper also

provides insights into the benefits and limitations of using transformers for computer vision tasks beyond image classification.

Zhi Tian, et al.[4] proposes a new object detection framework that combines the strengths of both regression-based and verification-based methods. In this paper, the authors introduce RepPoints V2, a model that represents each object instance as a set of representative points and learns to predict their coordinates and sizes using regression. Additionally, the RepPoints V2 model employs a verification module that learns to distinguish between positive and negative samples based on their similarity to the representative points, which improves the model's robustness to occlusion and cluttered backgrounds. The authors evaluate the RepPoints V2 model on several benchmark datasets and show that it achieves state-of-the-art performance on object detection tasks while being efficient in terms of computational resources. The paper also provides insights into the benefits and limitations of combining regression and verification methods for object detection and the potential applications of the RepPoints V2 model in real-world scenarios.

Xuebin Qin, et al.[5] propose U2-Net, a deep neural network that uses a nested U-shaped architecture to extract multi-scale features from the input image and produce accurate saliency maps. The U2-Net model consists of several nested U-shaped subnetworks, each of which combines features from different scales using skip connections and upsampling operations. The authors evaluate the U2-Net model on several benchmark datasets and show that it achieves state-of-the-art performance on salient object detection tasks while being computationally efficient. The paper also provides insights into the benefits and limitations of using nested U-shaped architectures for computer vision tasks and the potential applications of the U2-Net model in various domains, such as image editing and object recognition.

IV. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

1. Data preprocessing:

The first step was to preprocess the input image data before passing it to the model for prediction. This involved reading the image file sent by the client using the 'request' module in Flask, decoding the image data using OpenCV's 'cv2.imdecode' function, resizing the image to match the input size of the MobileNetV2 model, and applying additional preprocessing steps using the 'tf.keras.applications.mobilenet_v2.preprocess_input' function.

```
# Load the pre-trained model
model = tf.keras.applications.MobileNetV2()

@app.route('/predict', methods=['POST'])
def predict():
    # Get the image file from the request
    image_file = request.files['image']

    # Load the image from file
    image = cv2.imdecode(np.frombuffer(image_file.read(), np.uint8), cv2.IMREAD_COLOR)

    # Resize the image to match the input size of the model
    image = cv2.resize(image, (224, 224))

    # Preprocess the image for the model
    image = tf.keras.applications.mobilenet_v2.preprocess_input(image)
```

Fig 3

2. Model selection:

The MobileNetV2 model was chosen as the pre-trained model for this API due to its high accuracy and relatively small size. The model was loaded using the 'tf.keras.applications.MobileNetV2' function from the Keras library.

```
# Preprocess the image for the model
image = tf.keras.applications.mobilenet_v2.preprocess_input(image)
```

Fig 4

3. Prediction:

Once the input image was preprocessed, the next step was to pass it to the model for prediction using the 'model.predict' function. The output of this function was a set of predicted probabilities for each possible class in the model's output space.

4. Postprocessing:

After making a prediction with the model, the next step was to postprocess the output probabilities to obtain the predicted class label. This involved finding the index of the maximum probability using the 'np.argmax' function, and then using the 'tf.keras.applications.mobilenet_v2.decode_predictions' function to decode the class label from the output space.

```
# Get the name of the predicted object
class_names = tf.keras.applications.mobilenet_v2.decode_predictions(predictions, top=1)[0][0][1]
```

Fig 5

5. API development:

The Flask framework was used to develop the REST API for the image classification task. The 'predict' function was defined as a route that would handle POST requests containing image data. The function would preprocess the input image, make a prediction using the pre-trained MobileNetV2 model, and return the predicted class label as a response to the client.

```
# Load the pre-trained model
model = tf.keras.applications.MobileNetV2()

@app.route('/predict', methods=['POST'])
def predict():
```

Fig 6

```

if($file_size > 2097152) {
    echo "Error: File size must be less than 2 MB.";
    exit();
}

$file = curl_file_create($file_tmp, $file_type, $file_name);
$post_data = array('image' => $file);
$ch = curl_init();
curl_setopt($ch, CURLOPT_URL, 'http://localhost:5000/predict');
curl_setopt($ch, CURLOPT_POST, 1);
curl_setopt($ch, CURLOPT_POSTFIELDS, $post_data);
curl_setopt($ch, CURLOPT_RETURNTRANSFER, true);
$response = curl_exec($ch);
curl_close($ch);
echo $response;
}
    
```

Fig 7

6. Testing and evaluation:

The final step was to test the API using a set of validation images, and evaluate its performance in terms of accuracy and response time. The API was tested using various input images, and its predictions were compared to the ground truth labels. The response time of the API was also measured using tools such as the 'time' module in Python.

V. RESULT

The ads-free-web-based system allows users to upload images of products they wish to sell, and the CNN algorithm automatically detects and generates a description of the product. This eliminates the need for users to manually enter product descriptions, saving time and effort. Overall, with image recognition and automated description generation provides a seamless and user-friendly experience for both buyers and sellers. The ads-free-web-based system demonstrates the potential of image recognition technology in improving the functionality and usability of e-commerce websites.

Fig 8

Fig 9

1.

VI. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have transformed the field of computer vision and image recognition, providing a powerful tool for analyzing and interpreting complex visual data. With their ability to learn complex features and patterns from images, CNNs have become the go-to method for a wide range of applications, from autonomous vehicles to medical imaging.

In this seminar paper, we have explored the fundamentals of CNNs, including their architecture and training process. We have also examined the technical details of CNNs, including the different layers and operations that make up their architecture.

VII. REFERENCES

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